

Accurate adventitia reconstruction; significant or not in atherosclerotic plaque growth simulations? A comparative study.

Dimitrios S. Pleouras, Panagiotis K. Siogkas, Vasilis D. Tsakanikas, Michalis D. Mantzaris, Vassiliki T. Potsika, Antonis Sakellarios, Fragiska Sigala, and Dimitrios I. Fotiadis, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract— A reform in the diagnosis and treatment process is urgently required as carotid artery disease remains a leading cause of death in the world. To this purpose, all computational techniques are now being applied to enhancing the most cutting-edge diagnosis techniques. Computational modeling of plaque generation and evolution is being refined over the past years to forecast the atherosclerotic progression and the corresponding risk in patient-specific carotid arteries. A prerequisite to their implementation is the reconstruction of the precise three-dimensional models of patient-specific main carotid arteries. Even with the most sophisticated algorithms, accurate reconstruction of the arterial vessel is frequently difficult. Furthermore, there are several works of plaque growth modeling that ignore the reconstruction of the artery's outer layer in favor of a virtual one. In this paper, we investigate the importance of an accurate adventitia layer in plaque growth modeling. This is done as a comparative study by implementing a novel plaque growth model in two reconstructed carotid arterial segments using either their realistic or virtual adventitia layer as input. The results indicate that accurate adventitia reconstruction is of minor importance regarding species distributions and plaque growth in carotid segments, which initially did not contain any plaque regions.

Clinical Relevance— The findings of this comparative study emphasize the importance of precise adventitia geometry in plaque growth modeling. As a result, this work sets a higher standard for publishing new plaque growth models.

I. INTRODUCTION

Despite numerous studies on carotid artery disease, it remains a leading cause of death, highlighting the need for improved diagnosis and treatment methods. The carotid artery disease is caused by atherosclerosis, a disease characterized by the presence of plaque within the arteries, causing narrowing and stiffening and reducing blood supply to the brain, which is a major cause of strokes or transient ischemic attacks (TIA). Histological examinations of atherosclerotic plaques revealed the presence of cholesterol, calcium, fibrous tissue, and other cellular debris, while plaque composition is used by the American Heart Association to categorize them into eight different types [1].

*This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 755320, as part of the TAXINOMISIS project.

D. S. Pleouras, P. K. Siogkas, V. D. Tsakanikas, M. D. Mantzaris, V. T. Potsika and A. Sakellarios are with the Unit of Medical Technology and Intelligent Information Systems, Dept. of Materials Science and Engineering University of Ioannina, Ioannina, Greece (e-mail: dipleouras@gmail.com, siogkas4454@gmail.com, vasilistsakanikas@gmail.com, dmantzaris@gmail.com, potsika@gmail.com, ansake113@gmail.com).

The prevention of atherosclerosis involves either changing one's diet and exercising more or taking medication to lower blood lipids. In the event of an ischemic event, treatment options include medication and/or surgery. The initial treatment includes the administration of clot-breaking medication (intravenous tissue plasminogen activator (tPA)) as well as medication to restore breathing, heart rate, and blood pressure. However, clots can be surgically removed up to 24 hours after the onset of stroke symptoms in case tPA has no effect [2]

The biological process underlying the development of atherosclerotic disease is extremely complex. Several attempts have been made, nevertheless, to predict the growth of atherosclerotic plaques using computational techniques. A representative plaque growth model indicates that the atherosclerotic process is impacted by flow-induced shear stress on the endothelium membrane [3]. Endothelial function is altered in low-shear stress regions, increasing endothelial permeability and causing an abnormal buildup of low-density lipoproteins (LDL) within the arterial wall. The infiltrating LDL is oxidized by free radicals in the arterial wall, resulting in the production of cytokines and the initiation of an inflammatory response. Monocytes and T-cells, the immune system's fundamental cells, are drawn to inflammatory mediators (cytokines) in order to take up oxidized LDL, resulting in the formation of foam cells. Monocytes specifically differentiate into macrophages, while T-cells activate the macrophages to uptake oxidized LDL. Foam cells make up the majority of fatty streaks. Furthermore, T-cell cytokines cause contractile smooth muscle cells (SMCs) to proliferate and differentiate into synthetic smooth muscle cells that secrete collagen to heal the inflamed region. A few of the basic plaque species that are replicated include foam cells, artificial smooth muscle cells, and collagen, which results in a decrease in lumen area and an increase in wall thickness [5].

A few models exist that attempt to forecast the atherosclerosis progression. The vast majority of these studies use idealized 1D or 2D arterial geometries [4]–[7], while only a few proof-of-concept studies use actual human arterial geometry [3], [8]–[14]. Even in the last of them, there exist

F. Sigala is with the First Propaedeutic Dept. of Surgery, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Hippocraton Hospital, Athens, Greece (e-mail: drfsigala@yahoo.gr).

D. I. Fotiadis is with the Unit of Medical Technology and Intelligent Information Systems, Dept. of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Ioannina, and with the Biomedical Research Institute FORTH, University Campus of Ioannina, 45110 Ioannina, Greece (phone: +30 26510 09006; email: fotiadis@uoi.gr).

some, where adventitia reconstruction is neglected and replaced by artificially designed ones [15]. Although, several of these works include a validation part, their credibility is questioned regarding the lack of precise arterial geometries. In this work, we attempt to examine the significance of adventitia geometry in plaque growth modeling results.

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

A. Dataset

The current study included two patients from the TAXINOMISIS cohort who had >50% carotid stenosis. The dataset included patients' magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data (1.5-T whole-body system with a bilateral four-channel phased-array carotid coil) as well as clinical information (Blood LDL, Blood HDL, Blood Glucose, Hematocrit, Systolic & Diastolic Blood Pressure, Mass Flow Rate). Each patient who participated in the TAXINOMISIS clinical study (www.clinicaltrials.gov; ID: NCT03495830) gave written informed consent, and the study was approved by ethical committees.

B. 3D Reconstruction

To reconstruct the carotid arterial geometries, we used our in-house developed 3D reconstruction algorithm, which uses a variety of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) modalities, including ToF, T1w, T2w, and PD series. The reconstruction of the 3D model's lumen domain is based on the ToF series, whereas the reconstruction of the arterial wall and plaques is based on the fusion of the T1w, T2w, and PD series. Finally, the three resulting models' centerlines are aligned to form the final arterial model (Fig 1). The plaque growth model, which is partly described below, relied on the baseline 3D models.

Figure 1. Case examples of carotid geometries.
Left: 3D reconstructed lumen and adventitia layers.
Right: 3D reconstructed lumen and artificially designed adventitia layers.

C. Generation of artificial adventitia layers

The creation of two artificial adventitia layers for each of the two patient segments enrolled in this study is required for this comparative study. Each layer was generated as an offset to the corresponding realistic lumen layer, with an inter-layer distance of 1.64mm, the average thickness of the carotid wall [16].

D. Plaque Growth Simulation

The reconstructed geometries, along with clinical data from each patient, are transmitted into an existed plaque growth model, to enable the simulation of plaque growth [17]. This is performed by implementing the major biological processes of atherosclerosis in a four-step modeling procedure using several differential equations.

The first step entails a steady-state simulation of blood flow by implementing the Navier-Stokes equations for a laminar, incompressible, and Newtonian flow, which results in an evaluation of the endothelium's WSS (wall shear stresses) distribution.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho U_i U_j) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_i}, \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_{ij} = -\mu \left(\frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \mu \frac{\partial U_k}{\partial x_k} \right), \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} + \frac{\partial (\rho \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U})_i}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (3)$$

where, ρ is the blood density, \mathbf{U} is the blood velocity, P is the pressure, τ is the shear stress, μ is the dynamic viscosity.

The resulting flow-induced endothelial pressure is then used as an initial condition in a static structural analysis of the arterial deformation to evaluate the arterial wall strain distribution, by implementing a linear stress and strain equation.

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = D\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}. \quad (4)$$

where, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the tensor of the structural stress, D is the arterial wall's elasticity modulus and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the tensor of the structural strain.

Both the WSS and strain distributions are used as input to the next step, which is the simulation of mass transport and interactions within the arterial wall. The transmural flow of plasma in the artery wall, which is represented by the modified Navier-Stokes equations that take the porosity of the arterial wall into account, influences species transfer. Darcy's law states that momentum losses S_M result from permeability reduction.

$$\rho \gamma \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho (\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U})_i U_j) = -\gamma \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_i} + \gamma S_M, \quad (5)$$

$$\tau_{ij} = -\mu_{\text{plasma}} \left(\frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \mu \frac{\partial U_k}{\partial x_k} \right), \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} + \frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U})_i}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{K}^{ij} = \gamma \delta^{ij}, \quad (8)$$

$$S_{M,i} = -\frac{\mu_{\text{plasma}}}{K_{\text{perm}}} \mathbf{U}_i, \quad (9)$$

where, γ is the volume porosity of the arterial wall, \mathbf{K} is the area porosity tensor, which is a symmetric second rank tensor, μ_{plasma} is the plasma viscosity, while K_{perm} is the Darcian permeability.

Several equations that account for species dynamics are solved during this step, resulting in an evaluation of the plaque-induced strain distribution within the arterial wall. In particular, all of the species concentrations considered in the wall's domain are described by the modified convection-diffusion-reaction taking porosity into account.

$$\gamma \frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} ((\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U})_j c) = D \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\mathbf{K} \cdot \frac{\partial c}{\partial x_j} \right) + S_c, \quad (10)$$

where, c is the substance's concentration and D is the diffusivity.

There are three different pathways for blood substances to infiltrate the arterial wall: vesicular transcytosis, which accounts for intercellular transport, and transport through leaky and normal endothelial cell junctions. Trans-endothelial flow occurs primarily through normal and leaky endothelial junctions in the presence of endothelial dysfunction. Endothelial fluxes of lipoproteins (low density lipoprotein-LDL and high density lipoprotein-HDL) are thus defined by the Kedem-Katchalsky equations, which evaluate fluxes through bio-membranes based on pressure and concentration differences across them [17], [18]. On the contrary, monocyte and T-cell trans-endothelial migration is described by experimental equations, as it depends to inflammatory signaling, which is more intense in areas highly concentrated with oxidized LDL, and the magnitude of endothelial shear stresses, which prevents easy cell infiltration within the arterial wall in areas with high wall shear stresses. The concentration of nitric oxide in the endothelium, which is also described experimentally, influences the diffusive permeabilities of LDL and HDL [3], [19], [20].

Finally, a static structural analysis of arterial deformation is performed with the strain distribution as the initial condition, yielding the final wall thickness and lumen stenosis. A linear stress-strain equation is used to assess arterial wall thickening and lumen narrowing (Eq. 4).

III. RESULTS

Using the aforementioned plaque growth model, the species distributions and the corresponding lumen stenosis were predicted for all cases. Patient-specific data were used as input to the plaque growth model (TABLE 1), to ensure the realism of the results. In all cases, plaque growth was predicted for one year.

TABLE 1. PATIENT-SPECIFIC CLINICAL PARAMETERS USED AS INPUT TO THE PLAQUE GROWTH MODEL.

Clinical Parameter	Patients	
	Patient 1	Patient 2
Hematocrit (L/L)	0.443	0.459
LDL (mg/dL)	105	119
HDL (mg/dL)	46	69
Blood Glucose (mmol/L)	5.328	5.383
Systolic Pressure (mmHg)	140	150
Diastolic Pressure (mmHg)	80	75
Mass Flow rate in CCA (kg/s)	0.008824	01013686

Figure 1 depicts the predicted foam cell distributions in both patient carotid segments. A separation is made between the carotids with reconstructed and artificially designed adventitia layers, whereas the first are illustrated at the left and the last at the right.

Figure 3 depicts the final result of the plaque growth model, which are the resulted lumen and wall geometries after plaque growth. In particular, lumen geometries have been processed to intensify the stenoses by 10 times in order to highlight any differences.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this work, we presented a proof-of-concept study on the importance of the accuracy of the 3D reconstruction of the arterial wall and the role it plays on the subsequent plaque growth modelling process that has been introduced by our group. Two patient-specific arterial carotids were reconstructed in 3D in pairs, two having an arterial wall as produced by our in-house developed 3D reconstruction algorithm and the other two having an artificially reconstructed arterial wall. For the first pair, we observed that foam cell concentration is commonly distributed between the carotids with different adventitia configuration. The observed

Figure 2. Predicted foam cells distribution in both carotids. Left: Carotids with 3D reconstructed adventitia layer. Right: Carotids with artificially designed adventitia layer.

Figure 3. The predicted lumen stenosis in both carotids (scaled x10). Left: Carotids with 3D reconstructed adventitia layer. Right: Carotids with artificially designed adventitia layer.

maximum differences of the species concentration are less than 1%, which may be due to consecutive solver errors, and therefore, is of minor importance regarding plaque growth prediction. The remaining species of the arterial wall showed a corresponding similarity regarding their distributions within the arterial wall. Regarding the second pair, we observed that there are significant similarities between the carotids with different adventitia configuration. However, we also observe slight differences (<5%) regarding the degree of the stenosis in each case, which may have been resulted from computational errors, and therefore, can be neglected.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, it was assumed that accurate adventitia reconstruction is significant to plaque growth modeling, and therefore, this theory was tested on a state-of-the-art plaque growth model. Even though slight differences were detected between the carotids with different adventitia configuration, the results indicated the exact opposite of our initial assumption. However, the results of this study should be further validated by using a larger number of examined cases, as well as, by arterial segments with plaque regions.

REFERENCES

[1] J. Cai, "Classification of human carotid atherosclerotic lesions with in vivo multicontrast magnetic resonance imaging," *Circulation*, vol. 106, no. 11, pp. 1368–73, 2002.

[2] W. J. Powers *et al.*, "2018 Guidelines for the Early Management of Patients With Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Guideline for Healthcare Professionals From the American Heart Association/American Stroke Association," *Stroke*, vol. 49, no. 3, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1161/STR.000000000000158.

[3] D. S. Pleouras *et al.*, "Simulation of atherosclerotic plaque growth using computational biomechanics and patient-specific data," *Sci Rep*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 17409, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-74583-y.

[4] M. Guo, "Mathematical modeling of atherosclerotic plaque destabilization: Role of neovascularization and intraplaque hemorrhage," *Journal of theoretical biology*, vol. 450, pp. 53–65, 2018.

[5] J. Escuer, M. A. Martínez, S. McGinty, and E. Peña, "Mathematical modelling of the restenosis process after stent implantation," *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, vol. 16, no. 157, p. 20190313, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1098/rsif.2019.0313.

[6] J. Feng, N. Wang, Y. Wang, X. Tang, and J. Yuan, "Haemodynamic mechanism of formation and distribution of coronary atherosclerosis: A lesion-specific model," *Proc Inst Mech Eng H*, vol. 234, no. 11, pp. 1187–1196, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1177/0954411920947972.

[7] A. Corti, C. Chiastra, M. Colombo, M. Garbey, F. Migliavacca, and S. Casarin, "A fully coupled computational fluid dynamics – agent-based model of atherosclerotic plaque development: Multiscale modeling framework and parameter sensitivity analysis," *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, vol. 118, p. 103623, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.combiomed.2020.103623.

[8] A. I. Sakellarios *et al.*, "Prediction of Atherosclerotic Plaque Development in an In Vivo Coronary Arterial Segment Based on a Multilevel Modeling Approach," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 64, no. 8, pp. 1721–1730, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TBME.2016.2619489.

[9] A. Sakellarios *et al.*, "Prediction of atherosclerotic disease progression using LDL transport modelling: a serial computed tomographic coronary angiographic study," *Eur Heart J Cardiovasc Imaging*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 11–18, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1093/ehjci/jew035.

[10] D. Pleouras *et al.*, "Atherosclerotic Plaque Growth Prediction in Coronary Arteries using a Computational Multi-level Model: The Effect of Diabetes," in *2019 IEEE 19th International Conference on Bioinformatics and Bioengineering (BIBE)*, Athens, Greece, Oct. 2019, pp. 702–705. doi: 10.1109/BIBE.2019.00132.

[11] D. Pleouras *et al.*, "A computational multi-level atherosclerotic plaque growth model for coronary arteries," in *2019 41st Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)*, Jul. 2019, pp. 5010–5013. doi: 10.1109/EMBC.2019.8857329.

[12] P. Siogkas *et al.*, "Multiscale - Patient-Specific Artery and Atherogenesis Models," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 58, no. 12, pp. 3464–3468, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1109/TBME.2011.2164919.

[13] M. D. Mantzaris *et al.*, "Computational modeling of atherosclerotic plaque progression in carotid lesions with moderate degree of stenosis *," in *2021 43rd Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC)*, Mexico, Nov. 2021, pp. 4209–4212. doi: 10.1109/EMBC46164.2021.9630376.

[14] D. S. Pleouras *et al.*, "Prediction of the atherosclerotic plaque development in carotid arteries; the effect of T-cells," in *2022 44th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC)*, Jul. 2022, pp. 1590–1593. doi: 10.1109/EMBC48229.2022.9871632.

[15] K. Jesionek and M. Kostur, "Low-density lipoprotein accumulation within the right coronary artery walls for physiological and hypertension conditions," *Biosystems*, vol. 177, pp. 39–43, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.biosystems.2018.10.017.

[16] J. Krejza *et al.*, "Carotid Artery Diameter in Men and Women and the Relation to Body and Neck Size," *Stroke*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 1103–1105, Apr. 2006, doi: 10.1161/01.STR.0000206440.48756.f7.

[17] A. I. Sakellarios *et al.*, "Prediction of Atherosclerotic Plaque Development in an In Vivo Coronary Arterial Segment Based on a Multilevel Modeling Approach," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 64, no. 8, pp. 1721–1730, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TBME.2016.2619489.

[18] M. Cilla, E. Peña, and M. A. Martínez, "Mathematical modelling of atheroma plaque formation and development in coronary arteries," *J. R. Soc. Interface*, vol. 11, no. 90, p. 20130866, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1098/rsif.2013.0866.

[19] A. I. Sakellarios, "Modelling LDL accumulation in the case of endothelial dysfunction," *Journal of the Serbian Society for Computational Mechanics*, vol. 5, pp. 90–100, 2011.

[20] M. A. Bulelzai, "Long time evolution of atherosclerotic plaques," *J Theor Biol*, vol. 297, pp. 1–10, 2012.